

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The involvement of parents in decision-making regarding the academic achievement of students as perceived by secondary school teachers

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Abstract

This study determines the involvement of parents in decision-making regarding the academic achievement of students as perceived by secondary school teachers. In order to obtain an accurate and better understanding on the study, a quantitative-descriptive survey research design was employed using a survey-questionnaire that focused on the parents' involvement in decision-making regarding the academic achievement of students in terms of: a) supervising child's homework, b) observed and identifies the need of the children, and c) participates in their children's literacy process. The respondents were the thirty (30) teachers from secondary departments of Mindanao State University-Lanao National College of Arts and Trades. The results were tabulated using statistical tools such are: frequency, percentage distribution and weighted mean. It very undeniably that it is very important for students to excel in their academic studies, parents' involvement is the great factor that influence students' peak performance in academe. The results revealed that students' motivation is necessary for their academic achievement because it provokes students to persevere through challenges, eventually succeed. On the problem in supervising students' homework conveyed that parents had established a tone in monitoring their child's home works with a mean of 2.6. The results further implied that parents have greater extent involvement in their children's academic achievement. Likewise, on observed and identify the need of the children, it was perceived into "always" with mean of 2.7. The results express the parents understanding on the needs of their children. They recognized and monitor the developmental breakthrough of their children. Besides, participate in their children's literacy process was regarded the efforts of parents to maximize the development of their children's literacy. The results recognized the parents' involvement in decision-making regarding the academic achievement of the students was directly correlates to their children's academic success. While parents' involvement on students' performance is understood, the purpose is to sustain the learning, not to replace the students strive and responsibility.

Keywords: Parental Involvement; Decision-Making; Academic Achievement; Learners' Achievement

1. Introduction

Nowadays, students' lack of parental involvement in their education leads to several negative repercussions, including lower academic grades and increased attitudinal problems. Without proper parental support and guidance from their parents, students may struggle with their schoolwork, feel disengaged from their education, and face challenges in developing indispensable social and emotional skills. Studies show that parental involvement in decision-making regarding the academic achievement regarding supervising child's homework, observed and identify the need of the children and participate in their children's literacy process positively impacts students' academic achievement. According to Llego (2025), parental involvement leads to positive outcomes for students such are: When parents are involved in their child's education, the child is more likely to have positive attitudes towards school and learning, parental involvement provides support for the child both at home and at school. Studies have shown that children whose

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parents are involved in their education have higher grades and test scores and are more likely to complete their education and parental involvement can lead to increased communication and collaboration between families and schools. Moreover, the role of the parents in the academic performance of the students is multifarious and extends beyond mere inspiration. It surrounds emotional, stimulating, and pragmatic aspects. While emotional support contributes to greater resilience and stronger self-esteem, encouragement support fuels ambition and a love for learning of students.

As parents, they are the most influential persons in students' life especially in their education. Parents' actions, decisions and behaviours shape the way their children think, feels and acts. The children learned and followed everything that goes on around them. Aside from the practical benefits of parents' involvement on the students' academic achievement, it also helps to build a strong relationship between parents to their children and to the teachers itself. When the children observed that they are making decisions that prioritized their education, they feel valued and well care and loved. Moreover, in this study, figure 1, the conceptual framework of the study is made to illustrate and help researcher to conceptualize the problem at hand. This model was a projection of the system relationships among the variables that impact of parents' decision-making on the students' academic achievement as perceived by the teachers. These relationships were illustrated by the connecting arrows from box one to box two, and three. The boxes presenting the independent variable and dependent variable as well as the implications that derived from the results of the study. In box one (1), the independent variable, this includes, supervising child's homework. It is important to supervise the learners' output that needs to set aside a specific time and place to do homework each day per supervision of parents. Through supervision, it is necessary to check the child's assignments, projects and tests. Also observed and identifies the need of the children, and Participates in their children's literacy process. Parents should assess students' progress by analyzing their observations and need to find out about their children learning needs from their parents. From these, it can identify the children's interest and current development in school. While box two (2) presents how involvement of parents in decision-making impacted the academic achievement of students as perceived by the teachers using survey-questionnaire, and the third box, represents the implications that can be drawn from the results of the instruments used, whether through the survey-questionnaire and a follow-up interview from the respondents regarding their response on the questions.

Figure 1 Schematic Diagram of the conceptual Framework

2. Material and methods

This section comprises the research design, setting of the study, research instruments, research respondents, data gathering procedures and the statistical tools used in the study. Especially, this study sought to identify the impact of parents' decision-making involvement regarding the academic achievement of students as perceived by the teachers in Mindanao State University-Lanao National College of Arts and Trades. This study used quantitative-descriptive survey research design. The quantitative part of the study consisted of the results of the respondents' response to the research instrument and the results of the statistical treatment of the selected variables. The study was basically descriptive in nature. Data collection was based on primary data and secondary data. Primary data were collected through survey-questionnaire; the survey-questionnaire was created has two parts, part one, the demographic profile of the respondents, while part two, using relevant indicators for all the variables considered in this study answerable using three-point Likert scale. A set of questions were answerable by making choices, such are: Legend: 2.34 – 3.0 (Always), 1.67-2.33 (Sometimes), 1.00-1.66 (Never). Moreover, the secondary data, obtained from, suggestions from the teacher-respondents through interview to address the impact of parents' decision-making on the academic achievement of the

students. The questionnaire was focused on the parental involvement and its perceived impact on academic achievements of the students, this includes: supervising children's homework, observed and identify the need of the children and participate in their children's literacy process. At least thirty (30) teachers participated on the study from the secondary departments. Moreover, the researcher also utilized the following statistical tools in the interpretation and analyzing of the data gathered such are: frequency, percentage distribution, and weighted mean. The results were tabulated and properly analyzed and presented in table forms.

3. Results and discussion

This section presents all the results of gathered data from the respondents. The collected data were presented in tables, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly.

Table 1 Teacher - Respondents' Gender

Gender of the Respondents	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Female	28	93.3%
Male	2	6.7%
Total	30	100%

The table 1 presents the gender of the respondents. It reflects that majority of the respondents were female, with a percentage of 93.3% and at least 6.7% female. While it may appear that certain either private business or government sectors, more men than women are actually employed. However, there are some factors that might create the perception of female-dominated workforce, particularly in teaching. According to Elsesser (2024), women are more fit in teaching specially in preschool and kindergarten but according to her also there is no substantive proof to support the notion that women perform better in these roles but there is study found the following characteristics are most important for teacher effectiveness: passion about children and teaching, perseverance, risk taking, pragmatism, patience, flexibility, respect, creativity, authenticity, love of learning, high energy, and sense of humor. None of these characteristics suggest that gender should dictate who chooses this role.

Moreover, the problem on the involvement of parents in decision-making regarding the academic achievement of students as perceived by secondary school teachers, table 2 shown in terms of supervising learner's homework, the results connotes that parents was helping with homework, reviewing schoolwork and communicating with teachers about the concerns on their children. As it was shown in table 2 the indicators *"Parents should set up an ideal homework-friendly area with complete supplies"* and *"Homework area and time keep from distractions"* got the highest WM of 2.73 interpreted as *"always"*; followed by *"Parents schedule must have a regular study time of their children"* with a WM of 2.67 interpreted as *"always"*, *"Aside from Parents knowing the teacher of their child and she should also know the homework policies and how should they involve"* with a weighted mean of 2.6 interpreted as *"always"*. This implied that parents aware in balancing involvement into their children activities with autonomy. When parents are involved, the students were likely to complete their home works, bringing about to better retention of their knowledge and improve their academic impressive outcomes. While *"Parents should help the child making a plan to their studying time"*, lowest WM of 2.47. This suggests that sometimes it is not only the parents that need to decide about the study time, but the child should also have to decide. Over involvement of parents can hinder students self-directed learning and it can reduce their children's sense of self-efficacy and independence that making them overly dependent on their parents' assistance.

According to Chophel, T. and Choeda, U. (2021) in their study, they observed that repeated failure by students to do their homework affects both teaching and learning process and ultimately learner academic achievement. The parental involvement is very important in children's learning as it has a great deal of positive impact in the lives of their children. The children with parental help have proved to be doing well in their learning. Results were also support in the study of Jiayin Li, et al. (2024), it was emphasized in their study that parents play a crucial role in students' emotions, and their coping strategies significantly impact students' negative emotions. It was also noted that increased homework guidance can exacerbate students' negative emotions such as anxiety and depression in students. With high-pressure management styles can negatively affecting students' emotional well-being. Over-involvement can also reduce students' self-efficacy by limiting their opportunities for self-directed learning.

Table 2 Supervising Students' Homework

Statement	Never (1)		Sometimes (2)		Always (3)		WM	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%			
Parents should set up an ideal homework-friendly area with complete supplies.	0	0	8	26.7	22	73.3	2.73	Always	1.5
Homework area and time keep from distractions.	0	0	8	26.7	22	73.3	2.73	Always	1.5
Parents schedule must have a regular study time of their children.	0	0	10	33.3	20	66.7	2.67	Always	3
Aside from Parents knowing the teacher of their child and she should also know the homework policies and how should they involve.	0	0	12	40	18	60	2.6	Always	4
Parents should help the child making a plan to their studying time.	2	6.7	12	40	16	53.3	2.47	Always	5
Over-All Weighted Mean: 2.6									
Over-All Verbal Interpretation: Always									

Legend: 2.34 – 3.0 (Always), 1.67-2.33 (Sometimes), 1.00-1.66 (Never)

The results in observe and identify the need of the learners as perceived by the teacher-respondents in the involvement of parents presents in table 3. It shown that “*Observing the child’s behavior*”, ranked 5; WM 2.2, interpreted as “*sometimes*”, while “*discussing the child’s needs with their parents*”, ranked 1; WM 3.0, interpreted as “*always*”. Results connotes that teachers observed the lack in involvement of parents’ decision-making on students’ behavior. This can significantly impact on student behavior and development leading to issues such behavioral problems. Although less involvement on children’s behavior connotes that intrusive parenting style increased students’ independence and self-reliance, they become more resilient to face challenges. However, there is a big difference between healthy independence foster by supportive guidance from parents into neglectful parenting style, which can have noxious effects. But the results signify that discussing students’ needs with their parents was always done. They engaged in their children’s education; therefore, they can be better understanding their children’s learning needs and provide supports. This ensures that all the students’ needs to exhale in their academic performance were influenced by their parents. According to Hasegawa, V. (2023), parents play a critical role in their children's education. Being actively involved in their school life is essential for their academic and social success. Furthermore, parental involvement can help create a positive learning environment, foster better communication between parents, teachers, and students, and help parents stay informed of their child's progress and any issues they may be facing. In short, parents who are involved in their child's school life can make a significant difference in their academic and personal growth. This also supported by Rodriguez (2021), she suggests that a positive, warm and supportive parent-child relationship is the result of consistent and responsive parenting. It is likely that parent-child interactions that involve making social and future oriented decisions contribute to children’s development of this skill.

Furthermore, the involvement of parents in decision-making regarding the academic achievement of students on their literacy process was presented in table 4. Indicators, “*parents must ensure that children have ample opportunity to apply practices and strategies*”, ranked 1, VM 3, interpreted as “*always*”, and “*Parents demonstrate a positive view of education at home*”, ranked 2, VM 2.9, interpreted as “*always*”. The results implied that parents actively create opportunities these include providing a supportive environment for exploration, play, and hands-on learning experiences, both at home and in school. Likewise, “*Parent also should let their child read words and give spelling after*”, ranked 3, VM 2.7, interpreted as “*always*” and “*Parents should read stories and informational text to their children*”, ranked 4, VM 2.6, and interpreted as “*always*”. The results connote that parental involvement on students’ academic achievement significantly increase their children’s English language efficiency. The parents engage regular conversations with their children; significantly improve the students’ vocabulary and dynamics. Similarly, “*Parents ask their child’s teacher how they would like to communicate*”, ranked 5, VM 2, interpreted as “*sometimes*”, and conveyed that parents recognized their children learn from different ways. They provide a variety of learning opportunities for their children that accommodate various learning styles as can be observed from the indicators’ results.

As stated by Kantova, K. (2024), parental time spent with their child is the best investment in increasing the child’s human capital and that parental involvement builds children’s self-esteem, strengthens family bonds, establishes children’s positive behavior, encourages communication, and, most importantly it can also affect children’s academic performance. Moreover, parents have a strong influence on their children. They have a direct influence that is stronger than that of teachers and friends. For this reason, parents’ positive support towards their children’s education is considerable. It can aspire and empower the children to develop good learning habit.

Table 3 Observe and Identify the Need of the Students

Statement	Never (1)		Sometimes (2)		Always (3)		WM	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%			
Discussing the child’s needs with their parents.	0	0	0	0	30	100	3	Always	1
Discussing issues with the students and asking them questions.	0	0	4	13.3	26	86.7	2.87	Always	2
Talking to the child’s previous teachers and reading the information they have provided about the students’ learning achievements.	0	0	6	20	24	80	2.8	Always	3
Assessing the child’s, formally or informally, to determine their current knowledge, skills, and attitudes.	0	0	14	46.7	16	53.3	2.5	Always	4
Observing the child’s behavior.	4	13.3	16	53.3	10	33.3	2.2	Sometimes	5
Over-All Weighted Mean: 2.7									
Over-All Verbal Interpretation: Always									

Legend: 2.34 – 3.0 (Always), 1.67-2.33 (Sometimes), 1.00-1.66 (Never)

Table 4 Participate in their Children’s Literacy Process

Statement	Never (1)		Sometimes (2)		Always (3)		WM	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%			
Parents must ensure that children have ample opportunity to apply practices and strategies.	0	0	0	0	30	100	3	Always	1
Parents demonstrate a positive view of education at home.	0	0	4	13.3	26	86.7	2.9	Always	2
Parent also should let their child read words and give spelling after.	2	6.7	6	20	22	73.3	2.7	Always	3
Parents should read stories and informational text to their children.	0	0	12	40	18	60	2.6	Always	4
Parents ask their child’s teacher how they would like to communicate.	0	0	30	100	0	0	2	Sometimes	5
Over-All Weighted Mean: 2.6									
Over-All Verbal Interpretation: Always									

Legend: 2.34 – 3.0 (Always), 1.67-2.33 (Sometimes), 1.00-1.66 (Never)

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study and its analysis made, the involvement of parents in decision-making regarding the academic achievement of students in terms of supervising students' homework, observed and identifies the need of the children, and participates in their children's literacy process was positively perceived by the teacher-respondents. Parents established an unwavering homework space for their children, set a consistent schedule, and provide inspiration, while allowing them to work successfully on their own. While it is important for students to learn independently, parental support with students' assignments is important. It was also noted that parental involvement in their children education builds positive relationship between teachers, parents and students, vis' a' vis. They are able to work together to enhance students' academic achievements.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declared that he has no conflicts of interest related to this study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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